

Reimagining Digital Learning Game Design and Development: A Case Study

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Abstract: This paper explores a work-in-progress digital storytelling mobile application that leverages Generative AI, game mechanics and storytelling pedagogies to engage young readers and their caregivers. A collaboration across four organisations, this project articulates the beginnings of a sustainable model for developing educational technology and illustrates how educators, researchers, developers and industry can work together to create products that are viable and hold pedagogical value. Specifically, this paper articulates how each collaborator brings their expertise to bear, the challenges encountered and how they were overcome, as well as early user reactions from play tests of the mobile application. The mobile application is a component of a larger digital platform which has already been downloaded more than 60 million times. The platform is multilingual, covering 18 different languages. Through a demonstration of the platform and the work undertaken the project partners, this research showcases how industry and academia can successfully partner to co-design child-centric technologies that reflect pedagogical best practice.

Introduction

The global edtech market was estimated to be in the realm of around US\$146 billion in 2023 and is expected to reach approximately US\$549 billion by 2033, with a projected growth rate of 14.2% during the forecast period (Market.us, 2024). However, despite the enormity of its market size, the educational value of such tech offerings continues to be debated and the response to them amongst educators and educational researchers remains mixed (Escueta et al., 2020; Rodriguez-Segura, 2022). This can be partially explained by the lack of involvement of educators or educational researchers in edtech design and development, suggesting some compromise on its educational value during the process of creation.

This is an interesting phenomenon given the amount of educational research on technology-enabled learning. For example, personalised learning has been found to have a positive significant impact on learning (Li & Wong, 2021; Major et al., 2021), and game-based learning has been found to be positively associated with a myriad of student learning outcomes including cognitive, social and emotional development (Fernando & Premadasa, 2024). Educational research has not only demonstrated the positive effects of learning with technology but has also identified some key features that contributed to the measured positive learning outcomes. As such, the absence of educational research from the design and development of educational apps seems to be a missed opportunity. Based on the results of this case study, the researchers aim to address that gap by proposing a new working model for edtech design and development.

Impetus and Context

The launch of ChatGPT in November 2022 not only brought global attention to Generative AI, but engaged human imagination as the world grappled with and sought to harness this technology for a varied range of purposes (Tauli, 2023). Against this backdrop of furore and energy, there emerged questions as to whether the potential of Generative AI could be leveraged for informal learning and creative expression, and if so, how could be integrated with existing learning apps? This gave rise to a workshop to explore the integration of eBooks and Generative AI which was held at the University of Oxford in 2023. The attendees included educational researchers, tech

developers, corporate executives and interested stakeholders, which led to the genesis of a story app that features a library of stories co-authored by both human authors and Generative AI.

Over the British summer of 2023, a multi-organisational collaboration was forged with the shared goal of developing an e-book app that would embody evidence-based learning design and game design principles while leveraging machine learning and Generative AI capabilities. Through a process of iterative and participatory design, this e-book app is scheduled to launch in multiple regions across the world in September 2024. This paper is the first in a series of papers that seeks to describe a rather unusual but promising collaboration among international organisations to produce quality educational parent-child shared reading interactions through AI-powered mobile apps. Here, we outline a multi-organisation and multi-disciplinary approach to the design and development alongside early-stage user responses to the app.

Design and Development Process

The multi-organisation team responsible for designing and developing the app was drawn from an existing collaboration under the auspices of the Learning for Families through Technology (LiFT) project at the University of Oxford. Supported by Ferrero International (corporate partner) and Gameloft (game development partner), the project has sought to better understand the nature of young children’s learning through digital technology since its inception in 2017. It comprises multiple workstreams including creativity development (Booton, Hoicka, et al., 2021; Booton, Kolanali, et al., 2023), digital play, joint media engagement and vocabulary building (Booton, Hodgkiss, et al., 2021; Booton, Hodgkiss, et al., 2023; Booton et al., 2022). In 2023, Microsoft joined this collaborative project to help explore the potential for AI in early childhood learning technologies. The e-book work stream was added to LiFT in 2023 with a team comprised of representation at multiple levels from four different organisations and four different sectors, potentially bringing varied agendas and expertise to this project (Error: Reference source not found).

Figure 1 Multi-Organisation Design and Development Team

Error: Reference source not found shows the team’s levels of seniority across the four diverse organisations. Representation in the project from the senior leadership was crucial for high level negotiation of project goals and to ensure access to resources including human, financial and technological resources. At the working level, the involvement of middle management and specialist staff to provide educational research, design, development and operational expertise was necessary for delivery of a quality digital product. In addition, it should also be acknowledged that the complexities and workload of administration are considerable for a collaboration of such scale, and the cross-organisation coordination of support services such as human resource, finance and communications often require the intervention of the experts even though they may not be directly involved in the design and development of the e-book app.

Representatives from each organisation brought highly specialised expertise that was invaluable to ensuring the success of this project (Error: Reference source not found). The Oxford team included academics from Applied Linguistics, Child Development and Digital Education, forming the research pillar for this collaboration. This multi-disciplinary team leveraged both their domain expertise and academic skills to both conduct research and make use

of existing research throughout the design and development process. It should be noted that the research pillar was not separate from the design and development process; instead, it was very much embedded in the process and pivotal to it. For example, in the early stages of app conceptualisation, Oxford researchers drew from existing research evidence to identify story elements and themes that would inform not only the content of the e-book app, but also inform the user interface and user experience design. Plans were also underway to research specific app features after its launch, to iteratively improve the educational value and impact of this e-book app.

Figure 2 Sample Expertise by Organisation

The Ferrero team comprised managers and executives from digital marketing and brand management who played an instrumental role in project management, ensuring that the different entities were working collaboratively and productively. The team not only provided channels for continued open conversations but also facilitated these conversations, navigating and overcoming the different concerns and constraints which then moved this project forward. A particular roadblock encountered pertained to translation and localisation. Given the ambition of the team to launch the e-book app globally, quality translation was imperative. To this end, the team then quickly mobilised language experts in its various country offices and business units and worked closely with the rest of the team to ensure an adequate quality of translation and considering time and resource constraints, led the prioritisation of the languages to work on, in alignment with its launch plans.

The Gameloft team not only brought to the table their game design and development expertise, but also brought with them the *Appplaydu* platform, which was successfully launched in 2020 and downloaded more than 60 million times worldwide. The platform will house the completed e-book app, which would be made available at no additional cost to all *Appplaydu* users. The team also worked closely with all other stakeholders in this project throughout the design and development process, such as incorporating findings from educational research shared by the Oxford team and working with Microsoft data scientists on the backend coding and prompt engineering of the e-book app. One example of such close collaboration was the use of Generative AI to create accompanying images for the e-books created. Gameloft provided a library of existing graphic assets to train the engine and worked closely with Microsoft to ensure the quality of the AI-generated output, while Oxford guarded the bases of child safety and age-appropriateness.

For this collaboration, the Microsoft team focused largely on the use and integration of Generative AI. They led in prompt engineering and worked closely with the other stakeholders to incorporate the respective needs and collectively overcome respective technical constraints. In fact, both Microsoft and Gameloft had to make changes to their respective sets of codes as part of this collaborative problem-solving process during the design and development of the app. One example of incorporating respective needs pertained to the educational value of the e-books created and child safety considerations, which led to the expansion of the prompts from less than 10 lines to more than 100 lines.

As the sustainable development goals speak to the importance of innovation (SDG 9), partnerships (SDG 17) and education (SDG 4) as a blueprint for the future, there is evidence of value in establishing research-led partnerships with industry and technology leaders. When imagining a sustainable future for early childhood education systems and the potential to influence policy positively, there are lessons to be learned from such

collaborations, which motivated the documentation and study of this multi-organisation and multi-disciplinary approach to designing and developing an e-book app.

Research Procedures

This study was conducted using mixed-methods and an overarching interpretive research paradigm (Denzin & Lincoln, 2018). Firstly, semi-structured interviews were completed by nine key participants from across the four organisations who took part in exploring the potential for the use of Generative AI in a digital story book platform for inclusion in the Applaydu application. All participants were adults and provided informed consent. This interview was designed to elicit qualitative responses from individuals who worked closely on the project, focusing on understanding their respective perspectives on team dynamics, the design and development process and the product itself. All completed interviews were transcribed and coded for thematic analysis. Secondly, a questionnaire soliciting information on the resources invested into this project including human, financial and time resources was planned to be administered in late September 2024, after the launch of the e-book app. The questionnaire was designed to be a post-launch stock-take and review and sought to surface pertinent numerical information including intra-organisational team meeting hours and inter-organisational team meeting hours.

Story App Overview and Demo

Throughout the process of design and development, the team managed and resolved conflicts that arose as they sought to ensure the educational value of the app while managing corporate interests and technical constraints. Design features featured would include age-appropriate story complexity to ensure student engagement and word complexity tools to support vocabulary learning. Parent prompts were also included to facilitate joint-media engagement (Figure 3) and will be further explore here to exemplify the approach.

Figure 3 Pre Reading and Post Reading Parent Prompts

The prompts focused on encouraging dialogue reading between child and parent, promoting skills needed for reading development such as vocabulary building, connecting to background knowledge, and encouraging creative engagement. The challenge was to provide generic prompts suited to different story plots, such as overcoming the monster or a quest. They also include prompts for vocabulary building, asking children about the story's content, and encouraging them to find descriptive words in the text.

Originally, the prompts were text based and popped up on the screen. In the initial play test this approach was not well received by parents who frequently dismissed the pop up without reading. Learning from this, the researchers from Oxford and the designers from Gameloft collaborated to design a new approach using a much-loved Kinder toy character to simulate the adult-child interaction on the screen complete with enticing sparkles to alert them when the zebra had something to say. The new approach was tested and received excellent feedback from parents and children who took part in the play test which followed.

Preliminary Findings

Content analysis of the nine semi-structured interview transcripts found that differing priorities, conflicting timelines and ways of working could all be managed and that it is possible for collaborators from different disciplines and different organisations, operating from different parts of the world, to work as one team over a sustained period. Three critical success factors were found to have contributed to this productive collaboration among the four very different organisations. They are (i) shared mission and intrinsic motivation, (ii) time, and (iii) team values and culture.

Firstly, representatives from across the four organisations were aligned and focused on their shared goal to create a digital product with educational value for young children to enjoy with their parents/caregivers. Despite

these organisations having their respective agendas, they found common ground from which they could meet and collaborate. As one interviewee (M01) mentioned, “we were really working together to reach this the same result.” Another (F04) shared that, “we’re creating something really, really valuable and something really innovative at the same time” and she observed that even the “techie people” were excited, and this in turn stoked her passion for this project. These sentiments were echoed by another representative (M12), who shared that he felt everyone on the team understood “the value and the importance of this project and then was able to all become product owners. And when you become product owners, you really want your project to work, to be smooth.”

Secondly, comments from both Gameloft and Microsoft interviewees were surprising similar in terms of their commitment to this project. They saw this project as an opportunity to “research together” whilst learning from each other’s perspective. In the words of one interviewee (F01), there were “good people that are always, I mean available to explain and provide all the details.” This willingness to take time to articulate one’s position and explain things from one’s expertise were crucial to building a common understanding as well as a positive team spirit. However, this approach was indeed time consuming, requiring frequent check-ins and spontaneous meetings. At the pre-launch phase of this project, this multi-organisation team met daily for 30 minutes to align their work, taking the form of daily standups each morning. Weekly and bi-weekly meetings with middle managers and the senior management team from all organisations was also held to ensure alignment across all levels of all the organisations.

Finally, in terms of team values and culture contributing to the success of this project, many of the interviewees attributed this to the facilitation and mediation by the project managers, acknowledging in particular the contributions of Ferrero representatives in this aspect. These efforts have resulted in a positive working environment where “pointing the finger on you, saying it is your mistake. This never happen.... Every time we had a challenge, we work it together to find the best solution that that made me say” (M01). This was corroborated by comments from M12, who shared that “everyone was trying to help the others so that we all go into the right direction and have the output that we wished for.”

These preliminary findings illustrated how a team comprising representatives from different organisations and sectors working on the same project can enjoy a positive, collaborative partnership as opposed to an adversarial relationship. This was achieved through conscious effort made to engender a shared vision and activating intrinsic motivation, commit time and keep communications channels open, as well as growing a team built upon sound values and culture. As a result, this not only enabled the creation of a quality education product, but a team and a model of collaboration that could birth forth more quality educational products that incorporate educational research findings right from the onset.

Discussion and Conclusion

Just as Mattes and Dinkelaker (2019) confided that if anthropological fieldwork went to plan it would be a failure, the same could be said for technology projects. edtech design and development demands an agile and iterative approach. Just as ethnographers need to improvise and adapt to the demands of the field, so too do technologists working on the design and development of educational apps. As with any project, it is when disaster strikes that the strength of the team and its design is truly tested. In this case study, the problems faced, and there were many given the ambitious nature of working with such new and rapidly evolving technologies, were quickly solved through the actions of the team coming together to look at the issue from diverse backgrounds, perspectives and fields of knowledge. Guiding questions such as, “Is this feature technically viable?”, were congruent with conversations regarding the educational value of the feature and whether it would enhance or detract from the learners’ engagement and experience. Interestingly, the technical challenges were at times overcome through recommendations from the educational researchers, the game designers would inform the researchers of key learner analytics to support their evidence collection, and the AI data scientists would benefit from the educators’ refining their prompts and training data.

Overwhelmingly, this project has proven the importance of an agile approach to the design and development of educational apps that is best employed by collaborative teams of subject-matter experts. Lee Iacocca famously said, “I hire people brighter than me and then I get out of their way” (Iacocca & Novak, 1986). This has certainly been the lesson derived from this case study. When you bring together a team of people who are expert in their field, educational researchers, game developers, AI engineers and data scientists from leading international organisations, you achieve outcomes that are of increased value to the end user. The cognitive diversity of the team

engaged on this project has resulted in a more inclusive, accessible and child-centred approach to edtech that reflects the ethical guidelines for the use of AI shared by UNESCO (Miao et al., 2021; UNESCO, 2022).

Cognizant of the limitations of a case study approach, we recommend further testing of this model of collaboration across different projects and contexts and in the process build a corpus of case study that would allow for deeper gleaning of the principles of effective team formation, sustaining multi-disciplinary and multi-organisation collaborations and integration of educational research and educational technology division. Given the rapid pace of technological advancements and the huge investments made in edtech, it can only be imperative that we learn more quickly about how we can design and develop edtech products in ways that are both educational and sustainable.

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